

A comparative study of ketamine-propofol and ketamine-dexmedetomidine for IV sedation in short procedures – a randomized control study

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Abstract

For short surgical procedures, sedation is essential to patient safety and comfort. The degree of sedation, the duration of analgesia, and the recovery period are all greatly impacted by the sedative regimen used, which in turn affects operative results and patient satisfaction. The effectiveness, haemodynamic stability, and safety of two sedative regimens-ketamine-propofol (KP) and ketamine-dexmedetomidine (DK) in outpatient procedures are compared in this study. 140 patients having brief surgical procedures participated in the trial. They were split into two equal groups of 70 patients each, and each group was given a sedative regimen consisting of either ketamine-propofol (KP) or ketamine-dexmedetomidine (DK). A good comparison was made between the two groups because they shared similar demographic traits, process lengths, and ASA physical state. The DK group had a noticeably longer time to first rescue bolus, suggesting a longer duration of analgesia, even though similar boluses were required in both groups to accomplish rescue. There was no discernible difference in the two groups' awakening and recovery times. The DK group had less procedural interference, suggesting more stable sedation. Ramsay Sedation Score (RSS) were similarly matched at early time points. The DK group manifested a trend toward greater sedation scores at later times, which would indicate more stable sedation. Minimal adverse effects and similar occurrences between groups occurred, and no significant differences were detected regarding airway complications, nausea, vomiting, or recovery agitation. Both sedation regimens were well tolerated, with low rates of adverse effects. In summary, both ketamine-propofol and ketamine-dexmedetomidine regimens provided adequate sedation with similar recovery profiles. The DK regimen provided longer durations of analgesia, more stable sedation, and less procedural interference and was, therefore, an advantageous option for outpatient and day-care surgeries.

Keywords: Ketamine-propofol, Ketamine-dexmedetomidine, IV sedation

Introduction

Procedural sedation has become an increasingly important part of anaesthesia practice, enabling a patient to undergo the most diagnostic and therapeutic procedures minimally invasive without considerable hindrance towards comfort and safety. It represents the administration of sedative and analgesic agents that provide a state of consciousness in which the patient tolerates the procedure but retains protective airway reflexes and cardiopulmonary stability (1). The important objectives of procedural sedation include mitigation of pain, anxiety, and discomfort with minimal interference in normal vital function to make the experience better and the intervention successful.

This indicates that the correct choice of sedative should be made to achieve these goals, especially in short procedures, where speedy onset and recovery should be most important (2). Among the myriad drugs used in procedural sedation, ketamine stands out as unique for its dissociative anaesthetic characteristic. It ensures profound analgesia, sedation, and amnesia with retention of airway reflex and spontaneous respiration. As an intravenous anaesthetic agent stimulating the cardiovascular system, ketamine is better for patients with risks of hypotension. Its clinical application is restricted because of various side effects, including hypersalivation, nausea, and psychomimetic effects that range from hallucinations to agitation. Hence, side effects warrant a critical appraisal of combination therapy for increasing tolerability and enhancing its wider application (3).

Propofol is an intermediate-acting sedative-hypnotic drug often utilized in procedural sedation due to its rapid onset and short duration of action, along with an antiemetic profile. Suitable sedation, amnesia, and rapid recovery post-procedure are ensured by propofol. Propofol does not possess intrinsic analgesic properties, and besides, dose-dependent hypotension and respiratory depression exist, thus making it a bit difficult to administer to certain populations of patients. The sedative effect of propofol is combined with ketamine to enhance the analgesic and sympathomimetic effects of ketamine to obtain an optimal state of sedation with better stability of hemodynamics and fewer side effects (4,5).

The α_2 -adrenergic agonist dexmedetomidine is very selective and has increasingly been used for procedural sedation due to its unique profile of sedation and analgesia. It produces sedation that closely mimics sleep, with the ability to arouse easily and minimal respiratory depression. Dexmedetomidine also has significant opioid-sparing effects, so it is valuable in situations in which opioid use should be minimized. Despite these benefits,

dexmedetomidine has a slow onset and can cause bradycardia and hypotension. Hence, proper patient selection and dose titration are essential. The combination of ketamine with dexmedetomidine has a synergistic effect, minimizing the psychomimetic side effects of ketamine while enhancing sedation and analgesia (6,7).

Combination drug regimens, such as ketamine-propofol (ketofol) and ketamine-dexmedetomidine (dexket), have emerged as a strategy to exploit the benefits of individual agents while minimizing their limitations. It combines these anaesthetics since they take advantage of each drug's complementary effects, thereby offering the ideal balanced sedation profile that promises increased safety as well as higher efficacy. The popular aspects of ketofol include its fast onset time, smooth recovery, and steady hemodynamics, while deeper aspects of sedation, with a reduction in psychomimetic effects, characterize dexket (8,9).

Comparing the effectiveness, safety, and recovery features of ketamine-propofol (ketofol) and ketamine-dexmedetomidine (dexket) combinations for intravenous sedation in short procedures was the aim of this study. The ability of both regimens to induce drowsiness, the comparison of recovery patterns, and the frequency of side events are the secondary outcomes. In order to offer evidence-based recommendations on the best sedative combination for brief procedural interventions, this study methodically examines these aspects.

Materials and Methods

Over the course of three months, from November 2024 to January 2025, this prospective, randomised comparative study was conducted at Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli. The ethical committee approved the study before its start written informed permission was obtained. By comparing the mean and standard deviation of the time to the first rescue analgesic in the study by Kakarla et al., the sample size was determined using OpenEpi.com, as shown in Figure 1 (10). The calculated sample size was adequate to preserve the power necessary to record a significant difference between the two groups. A total of 140 patients scheduled for short procedures requiring intravenous sedation were enrolled and allocated into two groups.

Figure 1 – Sample Size Calculation using OpenEpi.com

Sample Size For Comparing Two Means			
Input Data			
Confidence Interval (2-sided)	95%		
Power	80%		
Ratio of sample size (Group 2/Group 1)	1		
	Group 1	Group 2	Difference*
Mean	8.72	10.82	-2.1
Standard deviation	4.47	4.02	
Variance	19.9809	16.1604	
Sample size of Group 1	65		
Sample size of Group 2	65		
Total sample size	130		

*Difference between the means

In this study, patients with ASA physical status (ASA PS) I or II, between the ages of 18–60 years, BMI from 18 to 30 kg/m², and patients undergoing procedures for less than 30 minutes were included. Patients with a known allergy or contraindication to ketamine, propofol, or dexmedetomidine were excluded from the study. Pregnant and lactating women, patients with severe systemic disease (ASA III or higher), and those with a history of psychiatric disorders or substance abuse were also excluded.

A full pre-anesthetic assessment of the patient involved taking a detailed history, physical examination, assessment of the airway, and appropriate laboratory workup to detect any contraindication to sedation. The fasting guidelines applied were the standard nil per os (NPO) requirements. The patients were instructed to avoid clear liquids for two hours and solid food for at least six hours. In the operating room, standard ASA monitoring was performed, including electrocardiography, respiration rate, heart rate, non-invasive blood pressure, and oxygen saturation (SpO₂).

All patients received intravenous fluid maintenance in compliance with standard perioperative guidelines, and an intravenous line was secured under aseptic precautions before the surgery. Midazolam (0.02 mg/kg) was used to provide a specific amount of sedation due to anxiety, ondansetron (4 mg) was used to avoid nausea and vomiting, and intravenous glycopyrrolate (0.004 mg/kg) was used as a premedication to minimise secretions. The loading doses for patients in group KP were 0.8 mg/kg of ketamine and 1.2 mg/kg of propofol. Propofol infusion rates were maintained at 30 mcg/kg/minute. Over the course of ten minutes, group DK participants received a loading dose of 0.8 mg/kg of ketamine and 1 µg/kg of dexmedetomidine.

The rate at which dexmedetomidine was infused was 0.4 µg/kg/hour. To make up for procedural interference, a rescue bolus dosage of IV ketamine (0.2 mg/kg) was administered when required. Each patient received oxygen at a rate of four litres per minute through a face mask. Bradycardia, hypotension, nausea, vomiting, and psychomimetic symptoms were

among the adverse effects that were seen and successfully treated. The study's main end measure was the time to the first rescue bolus of sedative. Recovery duration, sedation effectiveness, and adverse event incidence were additional secondary outcomes. The Ramsay Sedation Score (RSS) was used to measure the depth of sedation, guaranteeing the best possible levels of sedation while preserving patient safety.

All of the data that was gathered was compiled and analysed using SPSS version 27.0. The continuous data mean and standard deviation for recovery times and time to rescue bolus were displayed. The normally distributed data for the groups were compared using the unpaired Student's t-test. The chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as applicable, was used to evaluate categorical data, such as the frequency of adverse events and sedation efficacy scores, which were displayed as percentages. To find trends and differences between groups, repeated-measures ANOVA was used to evaluate repeated measurements of haemodynamic parameters at various time points. Statistical significance was defined as a P-value of less than 0.05. Data were shown using line graphs and bar charts to help show trends. To guarantee that the results could be interpreted with confidence, all statistical tests were two-tailed, and where required, adequate confidence intervals (95% CI) were provided.

Results

Two equal-sized groups, Group DK (dexket) and Group KP (ketofol), each with 70 patients, were created from the total of 140 patients. The demographic characteristics of each group are summarised in Table 1. The mean age of the patients in Group KP was 43.14 ± 8.1 years, while the mean age of the patients in Group DK was 44.15 ± 9.23 years. The groups did not differ statistically significantly ($p = 0.4925$). The mean weight of patients in Group DK (62.82 ± 7.15 kg) and Group KP (64.45 ± 11.8 kg) did not differ significantly ($p = 0.3247$). The average operating time for Group KP was 21.42 ± 4.61 minutes, whereas for Group DK it was 22.16 ± 5.12 minutes. The p-value was 0.3704, indicating that there was no significant difference between the two groups. Group KP comprised 46 ASA I patients and 24 ASA II patients.

In comparison, Group DK included 48 patients with ASA I and 22 with ASA II. Distributions were similarly uniform, yielding a p-value of 0.8953 to affirm the non-significance of differences between groups. These results signify that both of the groups in the study share baseline demographic and procedural characteristics equally, thus providing a matched comparison for additional evaluation of the efficacy of sedation, profile of recovery and hemodynamic stability.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

Characteristics	Group KP	Group DK	P-value
Age (years)	43.14 ± 8.1	44.15 ± 9.23	0.4925
Weight (kg)	64.45 ± 11.8	62.82 ± 7.15	0.3247
Duration (minutes)	21.42 ± 4.61	22.16 ± 5.12	0.3704
ASA PS I/II	46/24	48/22	0.8953

The summary of primary and secondary outcome measures for both groups is displayed in Table 2. The mean number of rescue bolus doses required was 1.56 ± 0.56 in Group KP and 1.53 ± 0.54 in Group DK, and no statistically significant difference was observed between the two groups ($p = 0.7475$). The time to the first rescue bolus was significantly longer in Group DK (11.24 ± 3.87 minutes) than in Group KP (7.62 ± 5.12 minutes), with a highly significant p-value of <0.0001 , suggesting that the analgesic effect was longer in the DK group. The time of awakening was similar in both groups.

Group KP had a mean time of awakening of 5.12 ± 3.02 minutes, while Group DK had a mean time of 5.32 ± 3.34 minutes ($p = 0.7108$). Recovery time was not significant, with a mean recovery time of 15.82 ± 4.23 minutes for Group KP and 16.21 ± 8.12 minutes for Group DK ($p = 0.7221$). Procedural interference, defined as patient movement or inadequate sedation requiring additional intervention, was significantly higher in Group KP (49 patients) compared to Group DK (32 patients), with a p-value of <0.0001 , suggesting better sedation stability with the dexket regimen. Though both regimens were successful, Group DK showed a higher time to the first rescue bolus and reduced procedural interference, which could indicate a better quality of sedation and duration of analgesia than Group KP.

Table 2: Comparison of primary and secondary outcomes

Outcome	Group KP	Group DK	P-value
Number of rescue bolus	1.56 ± 0.56	1.53 ± 0.54	0.7475
Time to first rescue bolus (minutes)	7.62 ± 5.12	11.24 ± 3.87	<0.0001
Awakening time (minutes)	5.12 ± 3.02	5.32 ± 3.34	0.7108
Recovery time (minutes)	15.82 ± 4.23	16.21 ± 8.12	0.7221
Procedural Interference	49	32	<0.0001

The RSS at different time intervals for both groups are summed up in Table 3. Baseline at 0 minutes, RSS was mean \pm SD as 1.21 ± 0.23 in Group KP and 1.17 ± 0.12 in Group DK, $p = 0.1992$, not statistically significant. By 5 minutes, sedation scores were elevated in both groups, with Group KP at 5.81 ± 0.34 and Group DK at 5.84 ± 0.13 , $p = 0.4916$, meaning early sedation effects were comparable. At 10 min, Group DK exhibited a more considerable sedation score compared to Group KP at 5.92 ± 0.35 in contrast to Group KP at 5.8 ± 0.46 .

However, this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.0846$). The scores maintained at subsequent time points for both groups did not show any alteration in deep sedation. At 15 min, Group KP reported a score of 5.79 ± 0.42 , while Group DK was 5.84 ± 0.28 , $p = 0.4087$. At 20 minutes, Group KP scored at 5.73 ± 0.45 while Group DK was at 5.79 ± 0.4 , $p = 0.4059$. At 25 minutes, it was 5.72 ± 0.35 for the KP group, while DK was 5.8 ± 0.33 ; $p = 0.1663$. Overall, both regimens achieved adequate sedation at all-time points, with neither differing significantly from the other. However, Group DK showed a trend towards higher scores at later time points, indicating more stability in the course of sedation.

Table 3: Comparison of Ramsay Sedation Scores

RSS	Group KP	Group DK	P-value
0 minute	1.21 ± 0.23	1.17 ± 0.12	0.1992
5 minutes	5.81 ± 0.34	5.84 ± 0.13	0.4916
10 minutes	5.8 ± 0.46	5.92 ± 0.35	0.0846
15 minutes	5.79 ± 0.42	5.84 ± 0.28	0.4087
20 minutes	5.73 ± 0.45	5.79 ± 0.4	0.4059
25 minutes	5.72 ± 0.35	5.8 ± 0.33	0.1663

Table 4 provides a summary of the frequency of adverse events in both groups. One patient from Group KP and two from Group DK experienced airway-related adverse effects; however, there was no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.5714$). Three patients from Group DK and two from Group KP reported experiencing nausea and vomiting. There was no discernible difference between the groups, as indicated by the p-value of 0.4121. Three patients in Group KP and four in Group DK experienced recovery agitation, which is restlessness or possibly a degree of confusion during the recovery phase. At $p = 0.7864$, the difference was not statistically significant. Both sedation regimens were well tolerated,

showing an incidental rate of adverse effects and no significant differences in their interventions.

Table 4: Comparison of Adverse Outcomes

Outcomes	Group KP	Group DK	P-value
Airway adverse effects	1	2	0.5714
Nausea and vomiting	2	3	0.4121
Recovery agitation	3	4	0.7864

Discussion

This study aimed to compare the efficacy of two sedation regimens, ketofol (KP) and dexket (DK), in a cohort of 140 patients undergoing short surgical procedures. The main objectives of the study were to evaluate how effective these regimens are at providing adequate sedation while simultaneously appraising recovery profiles and hemodynamic stability. Both regimens are used widely in outpatient and day-case surgeries, where there is a critical balance between effective sedation and minimal recovery times and side effects. The comparative evaluation of the regimens would refine the approach to the use of sedation in different surgery settings.

The demographic characteristics of groups KP and DK did not differ statistically at baseline. Age, weight, procedure time, and ASA physical status did not significantly differ between the groups, indicating that the patient populations in the two groups were similar. This is crucial because it reduces the possibility that confounding factors will affect the study's conclusion. Similar baseline characteristics would ensure that differences observed in primary and secondary outcomes would be attributed to the sedation regimens rather than intrinsic patient differences. Similar to the studies of Yagan et al., Kakarla et al., and Gao et al., this design allows for a strong comparison of the sedation regimens such that the conclusions are based on interventions rather than on patient-related factors (10-12).

Although the two groups received an equal number of rescue boluses, the time to the first rescue bolus was significantly longer in the DK group. The combination of ketamine and dexmedetomidine offered a more prolonged sedative effect because it took longer for patients to require additional sedatives. This means that the DK combination may provide a more stable level of sedation, which is of value in the outpatient setting, where the intention is to have a consistent level of sedation with minimal intervention. The prolonged duration of

analgesia is of particular interest in surgeries that require patients to be sedated for a longer period but should also recover quickly. Previous studies by Kakarla et al. and Canpolat et al. have shown similar results, where the addition of dexmedetomidine to ketamine improved the duration of sedation without significantly prolonging recovery times (10,13).

Despite the differences in the time to the first rescue bolus, there were no significant differences in the time to awakening or recovery time between the two groups. Both regimens lead to a quick recovery, and when the postanaesthetic awakening time was compared, it was observed that both groups tend to have approximately the same time. This is an important finding since it indicates that although DK might impart a more prolonged depth of sedation, it does not lead to delayed awakening or prolonged recovery, which is particularly undesirable in outpatient procedures, where timely recovery is needed. These findings align with Kakarla et al., Canpolat et al., and Amer et al., where dexmedetomidine was found to have no impact on the recovery period, although it affected the sedation time (10,13,14). Hence, the two sedation protocols are helpful for short procedures that require an interplay between the depth of sedation and recovery time.

In addition, the study rated procedural interference, the requirement for extra intervention by the presence of movement or insufficient sedation in the patient. The results showed that the DK group had significantly less procedural interference compared to the KP group, suggesting better sedation stability provided by dexket. This is an important outcome because it signifies that DK may provide a higher quality of sedation and, hence, less disruption during the procedure. This finding is in line with Kakarla et al. and Apostolos et al., who reported that the combination of ketamine with dexmedetomidine led to more stable sedation and reduced agitation during the procedure (10,15). In clinical practice, reduced procedural interference can improve the overall efficiency of the surgery because it may lead to fewer interruptions and a smoother surgical experience.

The degree of sedation at specific time points during the procedure was assessed by using RSS. Thus, there was no difference in RSS at the initial baseline point and 5 minutes between both groups. This means that during an acute phase of administration, the depth of sedation with both regimens is similar. However, at subsequent time points (10 to 25 minutes), DK had a small trend toward a higher RSS, indicating more stable and deeper sedation. Although these differences were not statistically significant at each time point, these trends could suggest that dexmedetomidine contributed to a more durable pharmacodynamic effect of sedation throughout the procedure. This is consistent with observations from Gunduz et al., Hegde et al., and Kakarla et al., who noted that dexmedetomidine was

associated with a more uniform level of sedation compared to other agents, which can result in a smoother anaesthetic experience (10,16-18).

The adverse event profile was favourable for both groups, with no significant differences noted between the groups regarding airway complications, nausea, vomiting, or recovery agitation. Low incidences of adverse events in both groups are reassuring, suggesting both sedation regimens are safe for use in short surgical procedures. It is essential for outpatient facilities in that it can reduce the likelihood of complications, which would then reflect the quality and outcome of their discharge and service to patients. The study shares similar findings by Kakarla et al., whereby both ketamine and dexmedetomidine showed very mild side effects within a similar demographic (10).

The ketofol combination offers a rapid onset with reliable sedation and a balanced effect. The fast-acting sedative profile of propofol ensures smooth induction and recovery, whereas ketamine provides analgesia with preservation of respiratory drive, helpful in maintaining safety during short procedures. This combination is also favourable for minimizing cardiovascular instability, where the smooth action of propofol combined with sympathetic stimulation of ketamine would maintain stable hemodynamics in the patient.

On the other hand, the dexket combination has several benefits that may make it especially useful for some patients (19,20). Dexmedetomidine is an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist that increases sedation without significant respiratory depression, which is an important advantage in maintaining airway patency. It also has anxiolytic effects, adding to the comfort of patients who are going to undergo short procedures (21). In addition, the longer analgesia provided by the DK combination reduces rescue boluses during the procedure and improves overall procedural comfort and, perhaps, post-procedural recovery.

The DK combination also demonstrated lower levels of interference with the procedure, which was indicative of good stability of sedation and thereby reduced the potential for interventions needed to correct inadequate sedation (22). Both regimens have minimal side effects. However, the DK combination has a more favourable hemodynamic and sedative profile and longer-lasting analgesia, making it particularly advantageous in cases where stable sedation and extended analgesia are required. Both regimens also have a relatively low incidence of recovery agitation and airway complications, making them safe and effective for outpatient surgeries (23).

The study has its shortcomings despite its outcomes. The study was carried out in a specific population of patients with short surgical procedures. Hence, the outcomes cannot be generalized to other surgeries or patients with a different medical history or a different

requirement for sedation. The study focused only on immediate recovery outcomes without carrying out any analyses on long-term recovery or even potential delayed side effects hours or days post-procedure. Future research could explore these longer-term effects in order to gain a better understanding of the relative strengths and weaknesses of each regimen.

Conclusion

This study provides revealing illumination on the comparative efficacy and safety of ketamine-propofol versus ketamine-dexmedetomidine sedation regimens. Both were suitable for use in short-duration surgeries with equivalent recovery time. Nevertheless, the ketamine-dexmedetomidine combination furnished longer-lasting analgesia and decreased procedure interference, suggesting it may even be a better stability agent for sedation. The two schemes possessed excellent safety profiles with minimal side effects reported. These results indicate that both sedation combinations are safe and thus can be used for outpatient and day-care surgeries, while ketamine-dexmedetomidine offers a potential advantage over the duration and stability of sedation and, therefore promises to be great in various clinical settings.

References

1. Tobias JD, Leder M: Procedural sedation: A review of sedative agents, monitoring, and management of complications. *Saudi J Anaesthesiol.* 2011;5:395-410.
2. Sidhu R, Turnbull D, Haboubi H. British Society of Gastroenterology guidelines on sedation in gastrointestinal endoscopy. *Gut.* 2024;73:1-27.
3. Banik S, Madavi S. Exploring the role of ketamine sedation in critically ill patients: A comprehensive review. *Cureus.* 2024;16:e65836.
4. Jose RJ, Shaefi S, Navani N. Sedation for flexible bronchoscopy: Current and emerging evidence. *Eur Respir Rev.* 2013;22:106-16.
5. Fulton B, Sorkin EM. Propofol. An overview of its pharmacology and a review of its clinical efficacy in intensive care sedation. *Drugs.* 1995;50:636-57.
6. Afonso J, Reis F. Dexmedetomidine: Current role in anesthesia and intensive care. *Braz J Anesthesiol.* 2012;62:118-33.
7. Bae HB. Dexmedetomidine: An attractive adjunct to anesthesia. *Kor J Anesthesiol.* 2017;70:375-6.
8. Kim JG, Lee HB, Jeon SB. Combination of dexmedetomidine and ketamine for magnetic resonance imaging sedation. *Front Neurol.* 2019;10:416.
9. Arora S. Combining ketamine and propofol (ketofol) for emergency department procedural sedation and analgesia: A review. *West J Emerg Med.* 2008;9:20-3.
10. Kakarla A, Senapati LK, Das A, Acharya M, Sukanya S, Pradhan A. Intravenous dexmedetomidine-ketamine versus ketamine-propofol for procedural sedation in adults undergoing short surgical procedures: A randomized controlled trial. *Cureus.* 2023; 15:e40676.

11. Gao P, Li S, Li Y, Zhao L, Luo Q, Ji Y. The comparison of ketamine-dexmedetomidine (ketadex) and ketamine-propofol (ketofol) for procedural sedation in pediatric patients: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Heliyon*. 2022;8:e11166.
12. Yagan O, Karakahya RH, Tas N, Kucuk A. Comparison of dexmedetomidine versus ketamine-propofol combination for sedation in cataract surgery. *Turk J Anesthesiol Reanim*. 2015;43:84-90.
13. Canpolat DG, Esmaglu A, Tosun Z, Akn A, Boyaci A, Coruh A. Ketamine-propofol vs ketamine-dexmedetomidine combinations in pediatric patients undergoing burn dressing changes. *J Burn Care Res*. 2012;33:718-22. 1
14. Amer AM, Youssef AM, El-Ozairy HS, El-Hennawy AM. Propofol-ketamine versus dexmedetomidine-ketamine for sedation during upper gastrointestinal endoscopy in pediatric patients: A randomized clinical trial. *Braz J Anesthesiol Engl Ed*. 2020;70:620-6.
15. Apostolos F, Nikolaos Z, Charalampos M, Kyriakos K, Sotirios F, Gregorios V. Dexmedetomidine-ketamine combination versus fentanyl-midazolam for patient sedation during flexible bronchoscopy: A prospective, single-blind, randomized controlled trial. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2024;24:301.
16. Hegde A, Joshi AB, Shankaranarayan UR, Manju R. To compare the efficacy of two intravenous combinations of drugs ketamine-propofol vs ketamine-dexmedetomidine for sedation in children undergoing dental treatment. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2021;13:529-35.
17. Gunduz M, Sakalli S, Gunes Y, Kesiktas E, Ozcengiz D, Isik G. Comparison of effects of ketamine, ketamine-dexmedetomidine and ketamine-midazolam on dressing changes of burn patients. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2011;27:220-4.
18. Sessler CN, Grap MJ, Ramsay MA: Evaluating and monitoring analgesia and sedation in the intensive care unit. *Crit Care*. 2008;12:S2.
19. Choi EJ, Kim CH, Yoon JY, Kim EJ. Ketamine-propofol (ketofol) in procedural sedation: A narrative review. *J Dent Anesthesiol Pain Med*. 2023;23:123-33.
20. Li H, Liu K, Yao L. Dexmedetomidine in combination with ketamine for pediatric procedural sedation or premedication: A meta-analysis. *Am J Emerg Med*. 2021;50:442-8.
21. Belleville JP, Ward DS, Bloor BC, Maze M. Effects of intravenous dexmedetomidine in humans. *Anesthesiol*. 1992;77:1125-33.
22. Yeter T, Gonen AO, Tureci E. Dexmedetomidine vs propofol as an adjunct to ketamine for electroconvulsive therapy anaesthesia. *Turk J Anaesthesiol Reanim*. 2022;50:114-20.
23. Mogahd MM, Mahran MS, Elbaradi G. Safety and efficacy of ketamine-dexmedetomidine versus ketamine-propofol combinations for sedation in patients after coronary artery bypass graft surgery. *Ann Card Anaesthesiol*. 2017;20:182-7.
